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DESIGN OF TOURIST DESTINATIONS AS A FACTOR OF STRENGTHENING AGGLOMERATION PROCESSES

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the design of tourist destinations as a factor in strengthening agglomeration processes. Recreational travel is an already studied factor in the formation of urban agglomerations in the industrial age. First of all, we are talking about dachas, recreation centers, school camps. However, at present, the character and goals of recreational flows have changed significantly in the direction of attending events and various agglomeration facilities by private vehicles. The core-city of the agglomeration, which has tourism as an industry of specialization, seeks to increase the time spent by tourists, incl. by expanding the geography of tourist attractions that can be visited in a day or two and returned to the core of agglomeration. Accordingly, for territories of the agglomeration, it is necessary to provide for allocation of space and engineering conditions for the creation of infrastructure designed to serve recreants and tourists. The article proposes to single out "narrow" and "broad" approaches to the design of tourist destinations. The "narrow" approach involves the design of new or reorientation of existing facility for tourist and recreational purposes. This approach is given attention in scientific and educational literature. When applying a "broad" approach to design, one should provide for the possibility of using a particular object not only for its intended purpose, but also provide for the possibility of using it as an object of tourist interest. The example of the Kazan agglomeration of the Republic of Tatarstan shows how purely tourist and recreational facilities function and how tourism industry becomes important for those who initially did not consider the development of tourism as a strategic goal when designing.*

Keywords: *city tourism, recreation, agglomeration tourism, city agglomeration, Kazan agglomeration*

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ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЕ ТУРИСТСКИХ ДЕСТИНАЦИЙ КАК ФАКТОР УСИЛЕНИЯ АГЛОМЕРАЦИОННЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ

Статья посвящена изучению проектирования туристских дестинаций как фактора усиления агломерационных процессов. Поездки с рекреационными целями являются уже изученным фактором формирования городских агломерации в индустриальную эпоху. Прежде всего речь идёт о дачах, базах отдыха, школьных лагерях. Однако, сейчас характер и цели рекреационных потоков значительно изменились в сторону посещения на личном автотранспорте событийных мероприятий и различных объектов в агломерации. Город-ядро агломерации, имеющий туризм как отрасль специализации, стремится увеличить время пребывания туристов, в т.ч. за счёт расширения географии туристских достопримечательностей, которые можно посетить в течение суток-двух и вернуться в город. т.е. за счёт агломерации. Соответственно, для территорий агломерации необходимо предусмотреть выделение места и инженерных условий для создания инфраструктуры, предназначенной для обслуживания рекреантов и туристов. В статье предложен выделять «узкий» и «широкий» подходы к проектированию туристских дестинаций. «Узкий» подход предусматривает проектирование нового или переориентацию существующего объекта для туристско-рекреационных целей. Именно такому подходу уделяется внимание в научной и учебной литературе. При применении «широкого» подхода к проектированию следует закладывать возможность использования того или иного объекта не только по прямому его назначению, но и предусматривать возможность использования как объекта туристского интереса. На примере Казанской агломерации Республики Татарстан показано, как функционируют сугубо туристско-рекреационные объекты, и как туристская отрасль становится важной для тех, кто изначально при проектировании не рассматривал развитие туризма как стратегическую цель.

Ключевые слова: городской туризм, рекреация, агломерационный туризм, городские агломерации, Казанская агломерация

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Introduction

Tourism as a branch of economics is of great importance for territorial changes, not only for territory where tourist facilities are located directly, but also for all territorial levels – from local to international. For example, development of one of the most popular types of recreation – beach tourism in countries such as Turkey, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Thailand and mass flows of tourists heading to these destinations from different countries at the turn of the 20th–21st century, meant not only formation of the hotel industry, parks entertainment, trade, international mass air traffic, excursion services, etc. in these countries, but also had a noticeable impact on territorial development in places where vacationers left. Impact can be traced not only in terms of income growth in these attractive destinations, but also in terms of export of earned money in place of permanent residence of recreants, as well as in active development of transport infrastructure in places of "exporting" vacationers – expanding network of international airports, their re-equipment, active development of the entire infrastructure accompanying transport hubs – from cafes, hotels to taxis; formation of such a service sector as tour operators and travel agencies, advertising and marketing segment of economics, creating jobs including in the field of personnel training for these new activities; wide development of information technologies for servicing tourists and corresponding jobs etc.

There is another important factor influencing active development of external tourist destinations for the region "supplier of tourists" and it is negative. Competition with active successful foreign destinations has been one of limiting factors in development of domestic tourism infrastructure. Of course, it can be legitimately argued that foreign destinations mentioned above as an example have undeniable geographical advantages – climate and sea coasts, which most regions of

the continental part are deprived of. However, fortunately, quality recreation options are associated not only and not exclusively with a beach holiday.

It is possible and necessary to see geographical advantages for recreation in any geographical conditions. For example, snow, with which our country is often associated, is our most valuable natural good, which allows us to organize a wide variety of types of recreation and events (as A. I. Zyryanov aptly said at one of the ARGO discussions). Variety of climatic, landscape and other geographical features is the most important advantage and a basic factor in development of tourism, of course, with due attention to tourist infrastructure – hotels, food, excursion services, transport and information components.

One of the important characteristics of tourism industry is its mobility both in time and space. Temporal dynamics of changes in external tourism over past 50 years demonstrates dependence of industry on many local and global factors – from economic crises and political events to epidemics, which is described in detail in the scientific literature [1–4].

Active growth in development of international tourism has been replaced by a sharp and, in fact, sudden for players in tourism market, not just a decline, but a fall during the pandemic. The period of early 20s had a dramatic effect on the spatial dynamics of tourism – some territories experienced a powerful outflow, while others, on the contrary, were not always ready for the influx of tourists. International destinations were losing tourists, but domestic recreational areas received overtourism. It quickly became clear that hospitality industry within regions was not ready for such a "stunning success"¹.

However, it is important to note that over the years of development of international tourism, there have been positive changes for regions and cities that have not previously specialized in tourism and hospitality. Due to the "flow of knowledge" in the field

¹ Deputy Minister of Economic Development of the Russian Federation: "Tatarstan is at risk of running into a shortage of hotels». URL: <https://business-gazeta.ru/news/580003> (Accessed on March 10, 2023) (In Russ.).

of tourism and hospitality, these territories have gained new experience in organizing events, creating new formats of recreation, for example, water parks, the diversity of club culture, cafes and restaurants, gastronomic offers and events, etc. has expanded. etc. Tourism exporting regions and cities have taken a fresh look at their unique features, which can become a magnet for attracting vacationers, and, in general, economic role of tourism in the local economy, at regional and national level, has become more obvious.

Results and Discussions

Issues of designing tourist destinations are becoming a strategic task for the socio-economic development of country, which is also reflected in programs of national projects. The national project "Tourism and Hospitality Industry" is intended to influence the achievement of the following national goals and targets²:

- opportunities for self-realization and development of talents;
- decent, efficient work and successful entrepreneurship;
- comfortable safe environment for life;
- preservation of population, health and well-being of people;
- digital transformation.

Solving issues of spatial development of the country as a whole and its individual regions, agglomerations and settlements requires a thoughtful approach to synchronizing projects aimed at improving quality of life of people in a particular territory. Understanding short-term and long-term consequences of made decisions including design of tourist destinations, is possible on the basis of a "broad" approach to projects of territorial changes and placement of certain objects.

Design of tourist destinations, in our opinion should be considered in two aspects – "narrow" and "broad". A "broad" approach means understanding presence and

manifestation of positive from the point of view of future formation of tourist flows, externalities or external effects from almost any human activity in space aimed at changing environment in a favorable direction. After all, tourism is an "all-encompassing" industry in terms of cognitive interest and the hunt for diversity and new experiences. Thing that for local population may seem ordinary and everyday life, for tourists may become the subject of display and interest.

The "narrow" aspect or approach to design of a tourist destination means that a particular object is created for tourism purposes, or an existing object is "reoriented for tourists". Design of tourist destinations, tourist and recreational clusters, its stages, classification of accommodation facilities and other tourist infrastructure, criteria for choosing a place for accommodation and other issues directly related to creation of a specialized tourist facility are described in detail in scientific and educational literature [5, 6].

So, Kruzhalin V. et al. distinguish following stages in formation of tourist and recreational clusters:

1. Administrative-and-managerial stage
2. Research stage
3. Design stage
4. Engineering stage
5. Management stage
6. Personnel stage

Authors consider the key factors in formation and development of tourist and recreational clusters and identify following groups:

- factors of outside environment – generating (political, socio-economic, institutional or regulatory);
- factors of internal environment – 1) resource (natural, cultural-historical, infrastructural, financial, labor, informational (including marketing)); 2) active (technological, innovative).

These factors can both activate and hinder creation and functioning of tourist and

² Passport of the National Project "Tourism and hospitality industry". URL: https://www.economy.gov.ru/material/file/da6490a6b838998e49df2556be17aaff/NP_Turizm_i_industriya_gostepriimstva.pdf (Accessed on March 10, 2023) (In Russ.).

recreational clusters [5].

When applying a "broad" approach to design of tourist destinations, it is necessary to provide for possibility of using this or that object not only by local population, but also by guests already at design stage. Obviously, different infrastructure is required for a local resident and a guest. First of all, for visitors it is necessary to provide places for food and sanitary and hygienic services, as well as the opportunity for rest and accommodation. In addition, clear city navigation, information centers and affordable communications are important in ensuring comfort of guests, and given the growth in independent travel, convenient and understandable schedules for public transport and private cars parking.

An example of application of a "broad" approach to design of tourist destinations is preparation of applications from cities to participate in the All-Russian competition of the best projects for creating a comfortable urban environment. Competition is held within the framework of the Federal project "Formation of a comfortable urban environment" of the national project "Housing and urban environment". Criteria for evaluating projects are following parameters³:

- 1) "Location – the validity of choice of location, relevance, synchronization of the project with national projects and other state and municipal programs";
- 2) "Preservation – preservation of the historical, urban and natural environment";
- 3) "Involvement – degree and variety of forms of participation of citizens, socio-cultural programming of territory";
- 4) "Forecast – predicted economic and social effects";
- 5) "Quality – quality of planning and architectural solutions"

As can be seen from the criteria, there is no emphasis on touristic component, however, the creation of a high-quality urban environment is an important specific factor in the development of city, both in terms of

living conditions of citizens and attracting tourists. And in this sense, there is synchronization with the national project "Tourism and Hospitality Industry" in terms of achieving the goal of "a comfortable safe environment for life".

Experience of participating in the competition of cities has already been accumulated and there are examples when the object created as a result of victory in the All-Russian competition became interesting for guests as well.

Fig. 1 – "Oreshkek" Park, Agryz (photo by the author)

For example, during expeditions to the Agryz district of the Republic of Tatarstan, interviews with townspeople showed that the "Oreshkek" park, reconstructed as part of the victory in the All-Russian competition, has become the object that townspeople consider to be shown to guests of the town and call it their tourist attraction "zest".

Another example of an object reconstructed as a result of winning the All-Russian competition is the beach in the town of Laishevo in the Republic of Tatarstan. The town of Laishevo is located on banks of the Kama River, is the administrative center of the Laishevsky district, which is part of the Kazan agglomeration. According to the 2020 census, more than 10 thousand people live in the town. Favorable geographical position – a long coastal strip on the Volga and Kama

³ All-Russian Competition of the Best Projects for Creating a Comfortable Urban Environment. URL: <https://gorodsreda.ru/konkurs2-2022> (Accessed on March 10, 2023) (In Russ.).

rivers, the low left bank of the Volga river and sandy beaches, vast areas of forests, including pine forest, proximity to Kazan have made the area a traditional place of recreation for Kazan citizens - dachas, school and student camps, recreation centers have been here for more than a dozen years of existence.

The participation of the town of Laishevo in the All-Russian competition made it possible to improve the long beach on the Kama and create a new beautiful and comfortable vacation spot for townspeople. Success of the project exceeded all expectations and on weekends there were, according to various estimates, 20-30,000 vacationers from Tatarstan and neighboring regions. The beach quickly became a trendy and popular travel destination, with holiday photos circulating on social media and thus attracting even more visitors. The very name "Laishevsky Beach" has become almost a household word in the everyday life of practitioners, i.e. a successful environmental improvement project for purposes of local population, but due to its high quality, it received serious externalities in terms of increasing the number of guests, which was not originally intended.

In addition to the Laishevsky beach in the same region of the republic, there is an example of appearance of a tourist attraction at the location of filming of the feature film "Zuleikha opens her eyes" – Semruk. The scenery created by settlement, beautiful coastal landscapes and the wide Kama River, as well as convenient transport accessibility, contributed to the flow of independent tourists and even small groups organized by local guides. On summer weekends, up to 1000 people came here, which could not but affect both the abandoned scenery and the surrounding area. This "germination" of tourist function has generated a request for reconstruction of the place in order to create comfortable and safe conditions for both tourists and local residents. And the project, already with a mention of recreational function, was submitted

to the All-Russian competition as the "Cultural and Recreational Cluster "White Mountains". The project won the competition and work is currently underway to improve and create necessary recreational infrastructure, incl. glamping⁴.

The Kazan agglomeration is rich in examples of tourist destinations that initially did not set the goal of attracting tourists as the main or most important, but successful projects for improvement of public spaces, restoration of historical and cultural sites, creation of modern IT infrastructure facilities later became important tourist sites on the map of the republic.

The Kazan agglomeration is a monocentric metropolitan agglomeration of the Republic of Tatarstan, the largest in terms of population in the region. The agglomeration includes five municipal districts (Zelenodolsky, Verkhneuslonsky, Vysokogorsky, Laishevsky, Pestrechinsky) and Kazan city district.

Using the example of the Verkhneuslonsky and Zelenodolsky districts of the Kazan agglomeration, one can trace how tourist destinations were purposefully created, and how initially the development of tourism was not a priority, but after a number of years the area became tourist centers.

Verkhneuslonsky district differs from other four municipal districts of the Kazan agglomeration in many ways – from the lowest population to the geographical location. The population of the Verkhneuslonsky district is the smallest among the municipalities of the agglomeration; moreover, it is even lower than population of the intra-city Kazan administrative districts (Table 1).

However, according to expert estimates, real population is 2 times higher and amounts to up to 30 thousand people, and in summer season up to 70 thousand people, since the area, having an extended coastline along the Volga and Sviyaga rivers, has been a recreational dacha for many decades area for Kazan, similar to the Laishevsky district.

⁴ Cluster "White Mountains" in Laishevo. URL: http://park.tatar/laishevo_konkurs (Accessed on March 10, 2023). (In Russ.).

Table 1 – Population of Kazan agglomeration, 2020⁵

<i>City, intra-city area, municipal district (MD)</i>	<i>Population, th. people</i>
Urban district city of Kazan – urban population – city of Kazan	1 308 660
Aviastroitelny district	118 106
Vakhitovsky district	85 005
Kirovsky district	140 001
Moskovsky district	133 168
Novo-Savinovsky district	222 926
Privolzhsky district	272 527
Sovetsky district	336 927
Zelenodolsky MD	169469
Laishevsky MD	61794
Pestrechinsky MD – rural population	62 094
Vysokogorsky MD – rural population	56 047
Verkhneuslonsky MD	17 495

A vivid example of designing a tourist destination specifically for purposes of recreation of Kazan citizens and attracting vacationers from other regions is the all-season resort-town "Sviyazhsky Hills". The "Sviyazhsky Hills" resort-town operates year-round and is known for its ski slopes and golf club, which ensures its all-season employment. Events are also held here – conferences, competitions, weddings, etc. The resort is provided with a developed infrastructure – 10 restaurants and cafes, 4 hotel complexes, more than 100 chalets. The resort is expanding number of ski slopes and accommodation options. Amid pandemic restrictions, the resort city experienced high demand for its services, which was confirmed by its imposition of restrictions on use of infrastructure only by vacationers in the resort, for example, or the need to book rooms in advance.

The design and creation of a resort-town in the Verkhneuslonsky district was justified by three main geographical factors – landscape and proximity to Kazan and the M7 Volga federal highway. The aesthetics of the landscape and panoramic views of the Volga, in addition to the cozy atmosphere of the resort itself, are its undeniable advantages.

Disadvantages include lack of public transport – the resort is designed for visiting by private car or sightseeing buses and has convenient parking for this.

Fig. 2 – Resort-Town "Sviyazhsky Hills" (photo by the author)

From the tops of the Sviyazhsky hills, a panorama of the city of the IT industry Innopolis, located in close proximity to the resort, opens up. Innopolis was designed and created as a modern city of advanced information technologies, as an "oasis" for the intellectual elite, with a high-quality recreation infrastructure – a sports center, a cafe on the first floors of modern buildings, an ArtSpace urban space, including a hall for events and film screenings, coworking, hack-space (a workshop where you can do aircraft modeling, robotics, assemble computers or make a birdhouse); theater and sound recording studio; visual arts studio; dance class; cafe. In the city, every third person is employed in the IT industry or scientific activities, and elements of modern IT infrastructure have already become attractions of Innopolis – an unmanned taxi, a delivery robot, etc. And if initially the city was positioned as a "paradise for its own", now it is understood that tourism brings its positive aspects. Currently, the city puts the development of the tourism industry as a priority. This is facilitated by the proximity to the all-season resort town "Sviyazhsky Hills" and the Island-city of Sviyazhsk.

Moreover, the goal was announced to become a place of agglomeration tourism, i.e.

⁵ Compiled according to the All-Russian Census of Population. Official website of the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation. URL: <https://rosstat.gov.ru> (Accessed on March 19, 2023). (In Russ.).

"so that not only from Innopolis residents go to Kazan, but also Kazan people come to rest in Innopolis".

On the border of the Verkhneuslonsky and Zelenodolsky districts there is a unique place in its history and modernity – the "island-city of Sviyazhsk". Since 1997, it has been administratively part of the Zelenodolsk municipal district. Local population is less than 300 people. The example of this place shows how achievement of the goal of reviving historical memory and significance for modern culture of the region becomes the driving force behind development of tourism in the agglomeration.

Fig. 3 – Delivery robot on the streets of Innopolis (photo by the author)

In 2010, the Republican Fund for the Revival of Historical and Cultural Monuments of the Republic of Tatarstan was established, the main tasks of which were formulated as follows: – "assistance in preservation, reconstruction, restoration of the Bolgar Historical and Architectural Museum-Reserve, the architectural and artistic revival of the State

Historical, Architectural and Art Museum "Island-city of Sviyazhsk", and other cultural values that are of value from the point of view of history, archeology, architecture, urban planning, art, aesthetics, ethnology or anthropology, social culture;

- promotion of cultural heritage sites;
- assistance in creation of scientific, cultural, intellectual potential of the Republic of Tatarstan".

As can be seen from the above quotation, goal of designing tourist destinations or tourist and recreational clusters was not set. However, the numbers speak for themselves.

Table 2 – Dynamics of the number of visitors to Ostrov-Grad Sviyazhsk⁶

Year	Number of visitors, th. people
2010	10
2011	17
2012	43
2013	108
2014	182
2015	261
2016	418
2017	491
2018	510
2019	663
2020	480
2021	899
2022	1388

Table 2 shows data from 2010 for the Island-city of Sviyazhsk. The increase in the number of visits by almost 140 times over 12 years indicates the super success of the project in terms of tourism development. Both Sviyazhsk and Bulgar demonstrate how actively tourism can develop based on interest in historical and cultural heritage and event events.

Thus, the Kazan agglomeration has rich experience in creating tourist destinations from the point of view of a "narrow" approach - the resort city "Sviyazhsky hills", but also the experience of the Island-city of

⁶ Compiled according to Results of the work of the State Committee for Tourism of the Republic of Tatarstan. Official website of the State Committee for Tourism of the Republic of Tatarstan. URL: <https://tourism.tatarstan.ru/documents.htm> (Accessed on March 19, 2023)

Sviyazhsk, Innopolis, the example of Laishevsky beach or the film set "Semruk" shows the need application of a "broad" approach to the design of tourist destinations, i.e. the importance of including the factor of potential tourist significance in the design, reconstruction, improvement of objects that have other goals than just the creation of a tourist and recreational cluster.

The use of a "broad" approach plays an important prognostic role for the development of the entire agglomeration. Taking into account the tourist potential when designing a particular facility in an agglomeration will make it possible to adequately assess the load on the transport system and take into account not only regular trips of the agglomeration residents, but also "spontaneous" or recreational goals dictated by both the residents of the agglomeration and other territories, i.e. agglomeration tourists.

Travel for recreational purposes is already a studied factor in the formation of the agglomeration. First of all, the classic variant of recreation for residents of a large city at dachas has formed and continues to form transport recreational flows of citizens and is characterized by certain weekly and annual cycles, i.e. intensify from the city on Friday evening-Saturday morning and into the city on Sunday afternoon, as well as with the opening of the summer season. The topic has already been well studied on the example of the Moscow agglomeration; there are also regional studies [7].

And, in general, it must be said that basis for the formation of urban agglomerations is the pendulum migration for labor, educational and recreational purposes was studied for the industrial period of the 20th century. However, now the nature and purpose of recreational flows have changed significantly. In addition to trips to summer cottages, this includes visiting various objects in agglomeration – from sports to cultural and educational events, holidays, etc. Such trips are made by citizens and residents of agglomeration, as a rule, without overnight stays and by private vehicles. Accordingly, for territories of the

agglomeration, it is important to provide for allocation of space and engineering conditions for the creation of the necessary parking lots, transport hubs, catering, sanitary facilities, etc.

It is also important to take into account that the city is the core of the agglomeration, which has tourism as an industry of specialization, to strive to increase the time spent by tourists through events and the expansion of the geography of tourist attractions that can be visited within a day or two and returned to the city. This state of affairs leads to the fact that tourists visiting the core city and staying in accommodation facilities located in the city carry out sightseeing trips to the agglomeration both independently on personal and public transport, and in organized groups. The lack and high price of accommodation facilities in the agglomeration pushes travelers who come for the purpose, for example, to visit the ski slopes or events in the settlements of the agglomeration, to stay in the core city, which has a variety of accommodation facilities, including price. This state of affairs leads to an increase in traffic flows, which is difficult to predict and regulate, and, above all, the movement of personal cars, and, accordingly, requests for parking, etc.

Conclusion

The tourism sector of the economy is known for its multiplicative influence on almost all areas of the socio-economic development of society. Cognitive interest, the desire for new impressions and new experiences of a person expands not only the geography of movement, but also the areas of activity and relevant objects that seem far from the concept of "recreation", for example, industrial tourism that is gaining popularity or visiting abandoned buildings and even creating in them tourist attractions and cafes or bars, agricultural tourism and visits to agricultural production. Similar processes and phenomena occur in a specific territory and lead to the fact that almost any human activity, the purpose of which is not the creation of a tourist product or display object, can at one time or another become a tourist attractor. That is

why we proposed to consider the process of designing tourist attractions, taking into account the "narrow" and "broad" approaches. The first of which has already been described in detail in the scientific, educational and practical literature, and the second should be approached carefully when designing almost any activity of society.

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